

LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF SIMILARITIES REPRESENTATIVE OF THE EXTERNAL WORLD OF HUMAN BEING IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Abstract: Figurative language tools are a great communication tool that is always used not only in English, but in all languages of the world. Figurative language tools help us quickly and effectively convey complex meanings or feelings that we want to express in speech. In English, figurative language devices are also called "figures of speech". In oral speech, we can use figurative language tools to convince the audience of our ideas or information, attract them and strengthen the psychological connection with them. In fiction, these figures of speech are used to explain the situations and events in the work or story more vividly to the readers. Adequate care is required from poets or writers while using these figurative figures of speech.

Key words: similarities, image, figures of speech, metaphor, comparison.

INTRODUCTION

The research conducted by the literary experts of the University of Arkansas showed that in English literature, mainly 3 artistic language images are used more. They are metaphor, similarities, diagnosis or personification. In addition, imagery, symbolism, hyperbole, juxtaposition, paradox and other language tools have their own place in English literature. However, it should be emphasized that the above-mentioned 3 figurative language tools play an important role not only in fiction, but also in the daily life of English people. These figurative language tools are usually used to express a creative approach to written or spoken language or to explain complex ideas. For example, when the British feel something unpleasant in their body, they try to express the extent of their condition by saying "butterflies in my

stomach". When expressing the difficulty of doing something, they use similarities like "like a moving mountain".

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

Research has shown that people are more likely to understand scientific discoveries, scientific concepts, and other scientific concepts when metaphors are used than when they are expressed in simple words. In general, figurative language tools are one of the main "figures" of oral and written speech both in fiction and in everyday life.

Similarities, metaphor and metaphor in English fiction.

In English, similarity is used when two objects or situations are compared to each other and is often expressed by words and conjunctions such as [like], [as]. The word "similarity" comes from the Latin word "similis" which means "similar". The use of similes in English literature dates back to the 15th century, and Shakespeare also used this figurative language in his works. There are many examples of similarities in English literature. For example:

"Her mystery piqued his interest like a door without a lock and key." ["The very mystery of him excited her curiosity like a door that had neither lock nor key."]

Through this sentence, the writer is used to express how much the secret of another person aroused interest in the hero of the work.

Rafael Sabatini also skillfully used figurative language in his "Sea Eagle". An example is the following analogy:

"He swung a great scimitar, before which Spaniards went down like wheat to the reaper's sickle.

In this similarity, the writer compares the number of Spanish soldiers to countless wheat in a field in order to describe them in a sweet way. Here, the farmer is embodied as the hero of the work, that is, he must destroy the "wheat" with his "scythe". The easiest way to distinguish between similes and metaphors in English is to pay attention to the words or conjunctions used in the simile or comparison. As mentioned above, simile can be defined by several words and conjunctions. For

example, in comparison, compared to, same, like, looks like, as as, etc. Metaphors, on the contrary, try to express an idea through events that occur in our daily life. They do not use similarity "elements" or adverbs. For example,

"All religions, arts and sciences are branches of the same tree". Albert Einstein. Out of My little years.

Translation: All religions, arts and sciences are branches of the same tree." Albert Einstein. In the above example, the scientist is using a metaphor and expresses the whole scientific truth through a single metaphor, that is, all religions (Islam, Christianity, Judaism, etc.), It is understood that science and science (natural and social sciences), worldly and religious knowledge in general have the same basis. By using metaphors, it can be seen that it is not so difficult to understand the exact and exact meaning of thoughts. Personification or personification [diag in Uzbek] is to give human characteristics to non-human or abstract things, such as physical attributes ("the eye of a needle"), emotional attributes ("a single shoe"), or human actions ("a leaf dancing in the wind"). For example,

"Because I could not stop for Death - He kindly stopped for me"

-Emily Dickinson, "Because I could not stop for Death"

Translation: That's why I couldn't stop death - it's the kind ones that stopped me. - Emily Dickinson, "Because I Couldn't Stop Dying"

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In short, when translating metaphors used in English fiction, it is very difficult to find and use metaphors from Uzbek that are meaningfully appropriate. One of the reasons for this is two different languages and different cultures belonging to different families. Consideration of cross-cultural differences and similarities is considered one of the most important factors in translation studies. Today, in-depth study of English literature, analysis of its shortcomings and achievements, researching the knowledge obtained from research into Uzbek literature, will allow further development in this field. From this point of view, it is necessary to increase the number of scientific researches carried out in linguistics.

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